

European Research Council
Executive Agency

Established by the European Commission

European Research Council (ERC)

ERC Data Management Plan

Template

ERC OPEN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

European Research Council
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Project Acronym	Project Number
ARCHI-SKIN	101044468

Template for the ERC Open Research Data Management Plan (DMP). The following sections should describe how you plan to make the project data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). Each of the following five issues should be addressed with a level of detail appropriate to the project.

SUMMARY (*dataset¹ reference and name; origin and expected size of the data generated/collected; data types and formats*)

The scientific data generated and collected during the project are related to the development of living coating system based on technically applicable, controlled, and optimized biofilm built by *Aureobasidium pullulans* a ubiquitous and widespread, yeast-like oligotroph fungus. The data will result from the experimental elaboration and characterization of fungal biofilm as well as characterization of materials (biomaterials, concrete, plastics, and metals, among others) that will be protected by the developed coating.

Types and formats of data generated/collected

Protocols: .docx, .pdf, .html

Chemical and physical analyses: .xlsx, .csv, .txt, .jpg, .tif, .pdf

Spectroscopic analysis: .xlsx, .csv, .txt, OPUS, ENVI, mat

Images (scans, optical and fluorescence microscopy, SEM): .jpg, .bmp, .tif

DNA sequences of the isolated strains: .XML, ASN.1, .txt, .ab1, .meg, .fasta, .gb

Molecular dynamic simulations: .mdp, .xyz, .gro, trajectory: .edr, .trr, .xtc

End-user survey: .docx, .txt, .xlsx, .csv

Movies: .avi, .mpg

Presentations: .ppt, .pptx, .pdf

Origin of the data

The data are either recorded from original experiments and measurements through software or transcribed on a computer from original notes and reports.

The definition of the data to be collected is detailed below:

¹ Several datasets may be included into a single DMP.

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Molecular dynamic simulations, computational docking used for the modelling and optimization of the best nutrient source and active ingredients compatible with selected fungal strains

Images: generated by various microscopes, surface topography maps acquired by microscopic observations

Chemical properties of materials indicated/predicted by spectral data in various ranges: FTIR (4000-400cm⁻¹), NIR (12000-4000cm⁻¹), UV-vis (280-1000nm)

Precise color and chemical mapping (combined spectral and spatial data) acquired by hyperspectral imaging in various ranges (macro scale) and FT-IR microscope (micro scale)

Thermal properties: proximate and ultimate analysis

Enzymatic and metabolic activities: microcalorimetry

Particle size and distribution: diameter, morphology and surface charge

Wettability and sorption: affinity of coated surfaces with water and other liquids, hygroscopic properties

Stability of coatings and appearance: microscopic analysis (drop size), macroscopic analysis (aesthetic properties)

Survey: distributional information including measures of centrality and variance, summary data. All data will be accompanied by narrative descriptions in reports and publications.

Expected size of the data

In summary, a maximum of 200 GB is expected. This amount of data can be stored at the existing facilities of the InnoRenew CoE without additional costs.

1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE (*dataset description: metadata, persistent and unique identifiers e.g., DOI*)

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Public data repositories: The ARCHI-SKIN project will follow the objectives of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable (FAIR) data management.

Primary data e.g., related to chemical and physical analyses, spectroscopic measurements, are published as supporting information of the corresponding manuscripts and archived on the Zenodo platform with reference to the grant number and related articles. All results of this project will be published in international peer-reviewed journals with digital object identifiers (DOI). Therefore, all data connected to publications will be shared according to FAIR principles, available long-term, and be quotable by DOIs.

Representative isolates of analyzed fungi are identified and deposited in the Ex Culture Collection of the Infrastructural center Mycosmo, MRIC UL, Slovenia (<http://www.ex-genebank.com>) at the Department of Biology, Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana. All DNA sequences of the isolated strains from this study are deposited in the GenBank database. The GenBank sequence database is an open access, annotated collection of all publicly available nucleotide sequences and their protein translations. It is produced and maintained by the National Center for Biotechnology Information as part of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration.

The ARCHI-SKIN team is also aware of new developments in Research Data Management (RDM) due to the steady development in technology; therefore, the research data management will be adjusted if necessary during the project.

2. MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE *(which data will be made openly available and if some datasets remain closed, the reasons for not giving access; where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited (repository?); how the data can be accessed (are relevant software tools/methods provided?)*

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Experimental data (related to multi-scale and multi-sensor characterization) will be stored with associated metadata including project subtasks and dates. DNA sequences of the isolated fungal strains are deposited in the GenBank open access database.

All results of this project will be published in international OPEN ACCESS peer-reviewed journals with digital object identifiers (DOI). Data sets will be uploaded and made publicly available on the InnoRenew CoE Zenodo archive located at <https://zenodo.org/communities/innorenew/>. Data will be identified according to a standard identification mechanism using type of experiments and associated standards and dates that will result in persistent and unique identifiers. For published data, the Digital Object Identification (DOI) will be assigned by Zenodo at the time of publication. All data connected to publications will therefore be shared according to FAIR principles, available long-term, and freely available.

3. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE *(which standard or field-specific data and metadata vocabularies and methods will be used)*

Data will be made interoperable by using standard IT infrastructure for data storage, processing, and access. Exports will be done in interoperable formats, such as JPG and PDF for images, and as text files for tables and spectra. Zenodo uses JSON Schema for internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular metadata formats. Controlled vocabularies will be used in descriptive metadata to support consistent, accurate, and quick indexing and retrieval of relevant data. To ensure interoperability, all metadata will use the same standards, while data will be provided in standard open file formats.

4. INCREASE DATA RE-USE *(what data will remain re-usable and for how long, is embargo foreseen; how the data is licensed; data quality assurance procedures)*

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Licensing the data to permit the widest reuse possible

The default choice will be CC BY Share Alike, but other Creative Commons licenses will be considered if needed.

Data availability for re-use and embargo periods

Most of the data will be made available for re-use as soon as they are uploaded on Zenodo, where they will be stored for at least the next 20 years.

Usability of produced and/or used data for third parties

The published data are usable by third parties during the project and after the end of the project without restrictions (according to the selected license). To increase data re-use, once the files will be made publicly available on Zenodo, the DOI links and selected metadata information will also be shared on the project webpage and on the InnoRenew CoE website and will be promoted through InnoRenew CoE and PI social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, ResearchGate).

Data quality assurance processes

- To assure data quality, the PI will check completeness, validity, consistency, timeliness, and accuracy of the datasets
- Whenever possible, standards will be followed for carrying out the experiments, allowing systematic parameters to be chosen and making easier the comparison of data by other researchers.
- The state-of-the-art equipment and software available for carrying out experiments at the InnoRenew CoE is of high quality and allows producing reliable data.
- Data storing procedures are well handled to avoid loss of data by saving raw files after recording and processing copies of dataset to be stored in another location.

Length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

The Zenodo repository guarantees accessibility of the data for its lifetime which is currently for the next 20 years at least. A suitable alternative will be considered in case of closure of the selected repository.

5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES and DATA SECURITY *(estimated costs for making the project data open access and potential value of long-term data preservation; procedures for data backup and recovery; transfer of sensitive data and secure storage in repositories for long term preservation and curation)*

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Data management with the above-described specific methodology to make the data FAIR is part of the PI tasks (estimated work time is 6-person months for the duration of the project), and service and infrastructure costs associated with data management are included in the budget allocated to the project (estimated associated cost 1000 EUR per year covered from the overheads). An additional budget of 50,000 EUR is estimated for the open access publication of 20 scientific articles. Zenodo is free to use so no additional costs are foreseen regarding the repository for making the data FAIR. Long-term preservation on the repository platform will not add extra costs, and availability of the data will be ensured. The project does not foresee producing sensitive data.

The PI will benefit from the data management systems implemented at InnoRenew CoE (following ISO/IEC 8000 and the SO/IEC 27000-series standards) which provide safeguards for data security, storage, and management. Privacy, integrity, and safe accessibility of all data collected will be ensured by the ICT equipment dedicated to storage, backups, redundancy, and security. The InnoRenew CoE has an internal intellectual property rights (IPR) management system to respect and protect data and knowledge owners. Research files stored on the internal data centre at InnoRenew CoE will be accessible only to authorized InnoRenew CoE employees. Other InnoRenew CoE employees can access selected subfolders either by VPN connection, or by coming to the InnoRenew CoE facility. The PI does not intend to transfer any sensitive data outside of the InnoRenew CoE infrastructure. The Zenodo repository has a strong privacy policy, which does not track, collect, or retain personal information from users. Zenodo's entire technical infrastructure has a restricted physical access to a limited number of CERN's staff with appropriate training and Zenodo servers get the latest security patches through OpenStack and Puppet configuration management systems.

DISCLAIMER. Please note that the ERC Data Management Plan is not a part of the Ethics Review. It is the responsibility of the Principal Investigator to inform the ERCEA Ethics Team of any ethics issues/concerns regarding the collection, processing, sharing and storage of data in relation to the project.